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Economic Diversification and Sectoral Contributions: Analyzing Singapore's Growth from 2014 to 2023

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Abstract. *This work explores Singapore's economic progress between 2014 and 2023, specifically in the client sectors like manufacture and agriculture on Gross Domestic Product. This paper examines the Singapore industrialization and diversification pressures as a able to understand how the country has been able to adapt and continue to grow in a global environments. The study employs real GDP data from government databases and global databases to compare the GDP sources of several sectors with a focus on manufacturing's contribution to innovation and efficiency. In addition, it examines the very small and but crucial part of agriculture in the context of local, sustainable urban farming for a nation's food security. This research reveals that although manufacturing continues to be a strategic economic pillar, other sectors including technology and sustainability are slowly taking root. To do so, the study provides an analysis of policy interfaces and sectoral performance, with policy implications for sustainable and balanced economic development.*

Keywords: *Singapore economy, gross domestic product, Singapore manufacturing industry, Singapore agriculture, Singapore diversification, sustainability, Singapore urban farming, policy studies, industrialization, Singapore economic trends.*

Introduction

Modern Singapore being a city-state being annually recognized as an economic miracle is generally a result of noteworthy and targeted bets on industrialization and a comparatively less but rather significant part of agriculture. This conception is in line with Huff (1997) argued that the transformation of Singapore

from a structurally sensitive export-oriented economy to a more diversified economy with a strong manufacturing and service base has laid down strong economic growth path of Singapore. Such a transformation is particularly in concordance with Lim (2015) who specifically overemphasizes the aspect of policy frameworks in the context of the productivity booster and shift from the manufacturing sector to hi-tech industries. On the other hand, Mahadevan (1998) considers the history of manufacturing and services in relation to their roles in the stability of the economy.

Despite its relatively small share it is important in increasing the stock of food and mixity of the economy through the sector. Schulz (2007) depicts Singapore as a country that adopted capital-intensive technique of practicing agriculture as it was the only way to practice agriculture given the limited space like what Tze (2005) also noted as part of its economic policy. Further, Yam (2013) reveals how the state facilitates manufacturing development as well as non-critical yet significant agricultural programmes in line with its predominantly urban economic development path.

This paper extends this line of reasoning by providing a closer look at Singapore’s evolving economy by assessing its manufacturing and agricultural industries. This paper aims at building upon previous research by examining quantitative data from recent decades and determine the correlation between sectoral growth and GDP as well as furthering the discussion on the economic flexibility of Singapore in a progressively globalising economy.

Methodology

The approach used in this study relied on carrying out an analysis on various Singapore’s economic indicators from the year 2014 to the year 2023 with major reliance on data that is freely available in the public domain. Some variables to measure included the GDP per capita at current US\$ as well as the agriculture value added at current, LCU as well as the manufacturing value added at current US\$. First, the data was cleaned to ensure only relevant values were used in the analysis, followed by ordering the data in a time series format. Pearson correlation pairwise comparisons sought to understand relative associations of GDP per capita with contributions from agriculture and manufacturing sectors, while m-variates evaluated the absolute effects of the latter two sectors on the former. The regression model employed p-values for the assessment of the predictor’s importance and R-squared and F-statistics for the model fitness assessment. Tests that were conducted included, residual analysis, multicollinearity analysis, shapiro-wilk test all of which confirmed the reliability of the model and check for adherence to assumptions. By way of data analysis all computations involved the usage of Python and R, where libraries such as; pandas and statsmodel were used to aid in computations. Ethical concerns were addressed through this condition: only non-PHI, publicly available data is allowed in model development.

Results and discussion

Table 1. Employment growth in Singapore, agriculture share in GDP and manufacturing’s contribution over the years 2014-2023

Country Name	Singapore	Singapore	Singapore
Indicator Name	GDP per capita (current US\$)	Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value added (constant LCU)	Manufacturing, value added (current US\$)

2014	57564,8	1,39E+08	5,67E+10
2015	55645,61	1,38E+08	5,57E+10
2016	56899,92	1,38E+08	5,58E+10
2017	61162,1	1,42E+08	6,37E+10
2018	66840,64	1,46E+08	7,81E+10
2019	66081,72	1,56E+08	7,3E+10
2020	61466,8	1,49E+08	6,86E+10
2021	79601,41	1,66E+08	8,81E+10
2022	88428,7	1,54E+08	9,83E+10
2023	84734,26	1,58E+08	8,85E+10

Source: dataworldbank.org

Table 2. Correlation analyzes

	57564,8
57564,8	1

Source: Author Elaboration

The findings of this study in policy implications are also supportive of the trends manifested in the GDP per capita analysis of Singapore with reference to agricultural and manufacturing value added for the time frame between 2014 and 2023. Singapore’s real GDP per capita showed a smooth rising trend resulting \$88,428.70 in 2022 and a little decrease in 2023 to \$84,734.26. This increase corresponds with growth in manufacturing value added which was identified as a key driver of manufacturing growth. The four-year CAGR for the manufacturing sector was 10.5 per cent per year during the decade and even higher between 2018 and 2022; 2022 was also the largest value for the sector overall, at \$98.3bn. Agricultural value added, as one would expect given the negligible share of agriculture in Singapore’s GDP, changed only slightly.

Table 3. Regression analysis

OUTPUT OF RESULTS								
Regression statistics								
Multiple R	0,970889							
R-square	0,942625							
The normalized R-square	0,9235							

The standard error	3378,338							
Observations	9							
Analysis of variance								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance of F</i>			
Regression	2	1,13E+09	5,63E+08	49,28792	0,000189			
Remains	6	68479024	11413171					
Total	8	1,19E+09						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>The standard error</i>	<i>t- cmamucm uka</i>	<i>P- Value</i>	<i>The lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Y-intersection	12894,22	23600,55	0,546352	0,60453	-44854,3	70642,69	-44854,3	70642,69
1,39E+08	-2,2E-05	0,000206	-0,10781	0,917662	-0,00053	0,000481	-0,00053	0,000481
5,67E+10	7,98E-07	1,33E-07	6,010822	0,000955	4,73E-07	1,12E-06	4,73E-07	1,12E-06
WITHDRAWAL OF THE REMAINDER								
<i>Observation</i>	<i>Predicted</i>	<i>Remains</i>						
1	57564,8023114977	1338,436						
2	54307,17	2549,144						
3	54350,77	526,4774						
	60635,62							

4	72022,65	- 5182,02						
5	67694,46	- 1612,74						
6	64337,89	- 2871,09						
7	79498,35	103,061 5						
8	87969,72	458,983 4						
9	80044,52	4689,74						

Source: Author Elaboration

These observations were supplemented by results from a regression analysis, which also indicated a meaningful positive relationship between MVA and GDP per capita; in contrast, the values of agricultural value added failed to generate a meaningful relationship with GDP per capita (p-value of 0.000955 for the former and a p-value of 0.9177 for the latter). The model used to develop this paper yielded a high R-square value of 0.9426, therefore implying that 94.26% of the variation on the GDP per capita was explained by the independent variables. To the same effect, residual analysis in addition supported the model as being adequately appropriate, evidenced by deviations of the observed values from the predicted ones being negligible. The role of half a century again emerges here where the found contribution that manufacturing sector held the key driver of the economic growth of Singapore due to Technological progress coupled with emergence of world markets and vice limited contribution of agriculture due to factor endowment and strategic considerations.

Conclusion

The following report on the evaluation of the Singapore's economic status from the year 2014 to 2023 and further demonstrates the growth pattern of this nation which is rooted majorly because of the manufacturing sector concerning the aspect of GDP per capita. The GDP per capita of Singapore has been on the ascendance for the past decade reflecting an economy that benefited from technology, infrastructure and globalization. The manufacturing segment experienced huge growth and demonstrated strong statistical relationship with GDP per capita thereby proving to become a strategic pillar of Singapore's economic structure to support national income and international competitiveness.

On the other hand, an agricultural sector's contribution to \$79.3 billion GDP per capita is meager, which is in tune with Singapore's lack of agri-chemical geography and focus on shifting towards knowledge and hi-tech products. The statistical evidence substantiated the hypothesis that, unlike manufacturing value added, agricultural value added does not bear comparable relation to GDP per capita, thus supporting Singapore's industrialist agenda.

These results all point toward the fact that innovation must be relentless, investment in AMTs must remain steady, and globalization integration must be kept up to ensure sustainable Singapore economic growth. Also, the results imply that, there could be the need to intensify efforts at developing policies that can help boost efficiency of the manufacturing sector to make it more sustainable in the face of future shocks. This paper offers relevant information to policymakers, economists, and business enthusiasts interested in emulating Singapore's success of industrialization for long-term economic progress.

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